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The Role of Innovative Technologies in Improving Speech Competence of Primary School Students

Sh. A. Utkirova,
NDPI master student

Abstract: *In this article, important issues related to ensuring the quality of teaching foreign languages to the young generation, forming communicative, linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic foreign language competencies of primary school students, the importance of innovative technologies in improving speech competence and their effective use are discussed.*

Key words: *innovative technologies, competence, communicative, linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, discourse competence, language skills.*

In the current period of rapid development, the focus on education and its development is also growing day by day. Today, it has risen to the level of public policy to educate young people comprehensively, perfectly, aware of every sphere and to provide the right guidance in gaining their status in society. The number of reforms and opportunities being created, especially regarding the study of foreign languages, is endless. Now, even in the process of education, new approaches, methods and modern technologies are required to be used more efficiently. In response to this demand, the teaching of the English language continues step by step, effectively using advanced technologies, from the lowest-preschool educational organizations, both in primary classes and in the non - philological directions of higher educational institutions.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev PD-5117 of May 19, 2021, of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to bring the popularization of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level", Resolution № 34 January 19, 2022 "On additional measures to improve the learning of foreign languages", Resolution № 610 "Measures to further improve the quality of foreign language teaching in educational institutions" August 11, 2017 about to ensure the quality of teaching foreign languages to the growing young generation at all stages of the continuous education system, to radically reform the system of training specialists who can speak foreign languages fluently get a qualification certificate based on improving, ensuring the integrity and continuity of educational programs in this direction, developing

a national test system for assessing the level of knowledge of foreign languages in order to give incentives to pupils, students and pedagogues, to encourage them, from the 2017-2018 academic year, the level of mastering a foreign language at all stages of the continuous education system, as defined in the State Educational Standards, we can give an example of priority tasks such as developing and putting into practice the evaluation mechanism based on the skills of "Listening", "Reading", "Writing" and "Speaking".

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 637 on Education adopted on September 29, 2020 also provides for the support of innovative activities in educational organizations and the implementation of educational programs using innovative technologies, the main goal of teaching a foreign language at all stages of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to form communicative competence in a foreign language in order to carry out activities in the daily, scientific and professional spheres of the students in a multicultural world. In this document, competencies are divided into the following groups:

Communicative competence of foreign language is the ability to use the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the foreign language in the process of communication.

Linguistic competence implies knowledge of language material (phonetics, lexicon, grammar) and acquisition of skills in speech activities (listening, speaking, reading and writing).

Sociolinguistic competence makes it possible to choose the necessary linguistic form and expression method based on a speech situation, communicative goal and desire of the speaker. Sociolinguistic competence includes socio-cultural competence and shows the ability to present national characteristics of authentic speech: knowledge of customs, values, rituals and other national-cultural characteristics of the country where one lives and compares it with the country where the language is studied.

Pragmatic competence implies the ability to get out of complex situations by repeatedly asking, apologizing, etc. when misunderstandings arise in a communicative situation in a foreign language under study.

In this Standard, discourse competence was included in pragmatic competence. This competence implies the expression of thoughts in oral or written speech using appropriate language means. Discourse competence refers to the ability to understand and interpret linguistic signals to ensure consistency and coherence in oral or written speech. However, there are different views on foreign language communicative competence and its components.

The term "Communicative competence" was created by Hymes, who emphasized that it is a broader concept than grammatical and linguistic competence. Chomsky on the other hand, believed that grammatical and linguistic knowledge was first, and then language use. M. Canale and Swain divided communicative competence into 4 competences: grammatical, speech, sociolinguistic and strategic. Bachman proposed a new model consisting of 3 components including several categories. Namely: language competences, organizational competences (grammatical and textual competence) and pragmatic competences (sociolinguistic and illocutionary competence).

The Council of Europe created a database on teaching foreign languages and included the following components in the gradual development of communicative competence: linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic (included as a sub-competency of strategic competence). As a result of studies carried out by Methodist scientists in our country and in SES, communicative competences are divided into the following groups:

Discourse (speech) competence within pragmatic competence implies expressing thoughts in oral or written speech through appropriate language means. Discourse competence refers to the ability to understand and interpret linguistic signals to ensure coherence in oral or written speech. Discourse refers to various meanings in the literature, i.e. language tools related to a certain context or topic of conversation, or the main unit of language, mainly the language of live communication.

It is known that the main practical goal of teaching English in elementary grades in accordance with the State Educational Standard for foreign languages of the continuous education system and the English language curriculum for general secondary schools is acquisition of communicative competence at the primary A1 level. The practical goal is achieved through the acquisition of linguistic (speech and language), sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies. In SES level A1 the competence requirements are defined as being able to know and use greetings, introducing oneself, thanking, requesting, receiving and giving information, apologizing, congratulating, making an offer and accepting/rejecting an offer. Linguistic competence according to SES consists of speech competence (listening, speaking, reading and writing) and language competence (lexical, grammatical, phonetic competences as well as graphics and orthography). Based on this goal, the curriculum distinguishes two aspects of teaching content: what to teach (language material) and what to do (listening, speaking, reading and writing). That is, by learning and teaching the language material (vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation), the acquisition of communicative competence related to the skills and competencies of speech activities is ensured. Exercises that serve to acquire linguistic competence, in turn, in the acquisition of knowledge about language material (phonetics, lexicon, grammar) and skills in the types of speech activities (listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing), serve to acquire sociolinguistic competencies, exercises to learn simple communication models in everyday situations, to strengthen the initial language skills, and exercises to ensure the acquisition of pragmatic competences, overt and covert expression of the thought expressed in a foreign language (conveying any information or idea, questioning, command, request, advice, promise, apology, congratulation, complaint) serves to understand and use their goals. The following exercises serve to acquire language and speech competences: Imitating the teacher or announcer (choral repetition, chain drill, repetition drill), changing the form of words (substitution drill), matching instead of points (article, preposition, modal verb, pronoun) fill in the gaps exercises are important for the acquisition of lexical, grammatical and phonetic competences.

Exercises such as TPR (Total Physical Response), Simon Says, Look and say, Bingo, Chinese whispers, Mime and gesture, Role play, Act out, Listen and draw, Cued dialogue serve to acquire speech competencies. English language teaching based on speech pattern, connecting language

exercises with speech practice and oral speech development were considered as methodological principles of English language teaching in primary education. In primary education, popularization of learning vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation units in speech samples is one of the appropriate actions. Drilling, that is, repetition and imitation (imitation) exercises aimed at acquiring language competences, are popular in the practice of English language teaching. They serve to eliminate formal, semantic, and functional difficulties of language phenomena. In such exercises, one or two language forms (grammatical or phonological structures) are repeated several times under the guidance and supervision of the teacher.

As a conclusion, it is possible to emphasize the need to adopt a deductive approach to the formation of the communicative competence of elementary school students, i.e. to achieve a greater share of standard communication models in their language reserve. Memorization of standard communication models and practice of purposeful application of them in speech situations play an important role in the formation of students' communicative competence. For this purpose, the teacher is recommended to form a base of standard communication models used in various speech situations and use them widely in practical training. Difficult situations may arise in objectively determining that elementary school students have acquired communicative competence in English at the A1 level. Unfortunately, in many cases, elementary school students' memorization of words, phrases, songs and poems, and roles in the form of scenes causes a false impression that the language has been learned and speech is developed. In order to prevent this, there should be textbooks designed to develop the speaking competence of primary school students and they should meet the following requirements:

1. to have the potential to ensure the acquisition of A1 level communicative competence specified in the SES curriculum;
2. to be able to ensure the integrative acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities from the types of speech activities in accordance with the curriculum and program requirements;
3. to be able to ensure the rational implementation of repetition (controlled) and free communicative exercises aimed at acquiring knowledge of phonetics, lexis and grammar from the types of speech activities, acquiring and developing skills;
4. to be able to ensure the mastery of the assimilation lexical minimum (pair of words, compound words, word combinations, examples of speech) with a high probability of usefulness in the acquisition of communicative competence.

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